

Newer Quinolines as Cardiovascular Agents

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1-(7-Trifluoromethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline-benzamido)-5-aryl- Δ^2 -triazolines (4a-h), 1-(7-trifluoromethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-benzamido)-2-oxo-4-arylazetidin-2-ones (5a-h), 1'-(7-trifluoromethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-benzamido)-3'-methyl-2'-oxothiazolidinones (6a-h) were synthesised by cycloaddition of diazomethane, mono-chloroacetyl chloride and thiolactic acid respectively, on the azomethine group of 7-trifluoromethyl-3-benzoylhydrazones (3a-h). The latter (3a-h) on diazotisation yielded 1'-(7-trifluoromethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-benzamido)-2'-arylformazans (7a-h).

CHEMISTRY of triazolines, thiazolidinones, azetidines and formazans has been explored from biological point of view^{1,2}. Furthermore, quinoline derivatives have also been reported to possess various pharmacological activities^{3,4}. This prompted us to synthesise some quinolino-azetidines, thiazolidinones, triazolines and formazans with a view to obtain better cardiovascular agents.

Compounds 1 and 2 were prepared by the reported methods^{4,5}. Compound 2 underwent facile condensation with aromatic aldehydes in absolute etha-

nol in the presence of piperidine basic catalyst yielding 3a-h. The significant feature of their nmr spectra was the appearance of a downfield signal at δ 8.85 (sharp singlet) suggesting the presence of methine proton of azomethine group¹ which is in conjugation with aromatic nucleus. Other important signals confirm that compound 2 underwent condensation showing multiplet at δ 3.37-3.45 (due to substitution at aromatic ring) and broad signals exchangeable with D_2O at δ 6.65-6.75 for amidic protons. Further, a sharp singlet at δ 10.10 exchangeable

Scheme 1

with D₂O indicates the presence of hydroxyl proton⁴ attached to quinoline nucleus, and multiplet complex at δ 8.10–7.60 indicates the presence of 8 aromatic protons. The ir spectra of the compounds showed presence of bands at 3 500 (OH), 1 720 (C=O), 3 400 (NH) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N). Furthermore, absence of signals in 3a–h at δ 1.50 (singlet) and 0.85 (singlet) for the presence of NH and NH₂ groups protons³ (which were present in compound 2) supports the condensation of hydrazino group with aromatic aldehydes. The molecular ions peaks finally confirmed their structures as 3a–h. The hydrazones (3a–h) on 1,3-dipolar condensation with diazomethane in dry THF-ether mixture at 15° for 15 days yielded 4a–h. Nmr spectra showed signal at δ 6.40 (triplet) and 5.90 (doublet) for methine and methylene protons of trizolines respectively. Moreover, the presence of ir bands at 1 429 (N=N) and 1 520 cm⁻¹ (N–N) and molecular ion peaks finally confirmed their structures. The anils (3a–h) on cyclocondensation with monochloroacetyl chloride in dry DMF in the presence of triethylamine yielded 5a–h. The appearance of nmr signals at δ 4.85 (d, ArCH) and 5.54 (d, CHCl) and the presence of an additional bands at 1 740 (C=O β -lactam ring) and 1 500 cm⁻¹ (C–N) supports the 1,3-dipolar condensation of monochloroacetyl chloride on azomethine group of 3a–h

yielding 5a–h. The absence of sharp singlet at δ 8.85 for methine protons in 3a–h is another evidence for formation of these compounds. Molecular ion peaks [M]⁺ finally confirmed their structures. Similarly, 1,3-dipolar condensation of 3a–h with thiolactic acid yielded 6a–h. The presence of a downfield signal at δ 6.55 (singlet for methine proton adjacent to aromatic nucleus), 5.70 (quadrant for methine proton attached to the methyl group of β -thialactam ring) and 4.90 (doublet for three protons of CH₃ group of thiazolidinones) confirmed cyclocondensation. The presence of β -thialactam ring is further confirmed due to appearance of ir band at 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Molecular ion peaks [M]⁺ finally confirmed the structures of 6a–h. Diazotisation of 3a–h produced corresponding formazans 7a–h. The presence of ir bands at 1 590 (C=N), 1 500 (C–N) and 1 429 cm⁻¹ (N=N) confirmed their structures. The structures were further confirmed by the presence of molecular ion peaks [M]⁺ in the mass spectra.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on an EM-360 (60 Hz)

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL** DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Mol. formula (Mol. weight)	Molecular ion peaks [M] ⁺ (% intensity)
3a	H	—	288	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (359)	359(3)
3b	2-OCH ₃	—	293	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (389)	389(4.5)
3c	3-OCH ₃	—	290	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (389)	389(4.0)
3d	4-OCH ₃	—	287	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (389)	389(4.0)
3e	2-Cl	—	300	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ Cl (393.5)	394(10.0)
3f	3-Cl	—	312	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ Cl (393.5)	394(9.5)
3g	4-Cl	—	302	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ Cl (393.5)	393(2.5)
3h	2-F	—	320	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ F ₄ (377)	377(15.0)
4a	H	—	176	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (401)	401(20.0)
4b	2-OCH ₃	—	203	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (431)	431(12.0)
4c	3-OCH ₃	—	256	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (431)	430(9.5)
4d	4-OCH ₃	—	267	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (431)	431(15.0)
4e	2-Cl	—	217	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ Cl (435.5)	436(5.0)
4f	3-Cl	—	263	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ Cl (435.5)	436(5.5)
4g	4-Cl	—	277	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ Cl (435.5)	434(10.0)
4h	2-F	—	293	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ F ₄ (420.0)	420(20.0)
5a	H	—	156	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ ClF ₂ (465.5)	436(3.5)
5b	2-OCH ₃	—	215	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ ClF ₂ (465.5)	465(2.5)
5c	3-OCH ₃	—	276	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ ClF ₂ (465.5)	465(2.0)

(Table 1 contd.)

5d	4-OCH ₃	—	223	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ ClF ₂ (465.5)	465(1.5)
5e	2-Cl	—	254	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ (465.5)	465(7.5)
5f	3-Cl	—	283	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ (465.5)	465(5.0)
5g	4-Cl	—	286	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ (470.0)	470(4.0)
5h	2-F	—	234	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ F ₄ (418.0)	418(8.5)
6a	H	—	295	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ SF ₂ (447)	446(12.0)
6b	2-OCH ₃	—	303	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ SF ₂ (477.0)	477(10.0)
6c	3-OCH ₃	—	283	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ SF ₂ (477.0)	477(8.5)
6d	4-OCH ₃	—	301	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ SF ₂ (477.0)	477(6.5)
6e	2-Cl	—	281	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ SF ₂ Cl (481.5)	481(4.0)
6f	3-Cl	—	311	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ SF ₂ Cl (481.5)	481(4.0)
6g	4-Cl	—	293	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ SF ₂ Cl (481.5)	481(10.0)
6h	2-F	—	295	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ SF ₄ (481.5)	481(10.0)
7a	H	2-Cl	176	C ₂₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ ClF ₂ (497.5)	498(5.5)
7b	2-OCH ₃	2,4-(Cl) ₂	156	C ₂₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ (562)	562(4.5)
7c	3-OCH ₃	2-CH ₃	137	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ (507.0)	507(9.5)
7d	4-OCH ₃	2-OCH ₃	201	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ F ₂ (523.0)	523(20.0)
7e	2-Cl	2-Cl	232	C ₂₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ (532.0)	532(25.0)
7f	3-Cl	4-Cl	247	C ₂₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ (532.0)	532(20.0)
7g	4-Cl	4-Cl	145	C ₂₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂ (532.0)	532(18.0)
7h	2-F	2,4-(Cl) ₂	167	C ₂₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₄ (550.0)	550(2.5)

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis ; Yield of compounds : 25-65%.

**3b $\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 1 720 (CO), 3 400 (NH), 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N), δ (CDCl₃) 8.10-7.60 (8H, m, ArH), 10.50 (1H, ss, ArOH exchangeable), 8.85 (1H, ss, CH=N), 6.65-6.75 (1H, bs, CONH exchangeable), 3.40 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 4b $\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 3 400 (OH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 520 (N-N), 1 429 cm⁻¹ (N=N) δ (CDCl₃) 8.70-7.50 (8H, m, ArH), 10.40 (1H, ss, ArOH exchangeable), 6.70-6.60 (1H, bs, CONH exchangeable), 6.40 (1H, t, CH of triazolone ring), 5.90 (2H, d, CH₂ of triazolone ring), 5b $\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 3 400 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 740 (C=O of β -lactam ring), 3 000 (CH), 1 520 cm⁻¹ (CN), δ (DMSO-d₆) 8.60-7.30 (8H, m, ArH), 10.10 (1H, ss, ArOH exchangeable), 5.90 (1H, hump, CONH exchangeable), 5.45 (1H, d, ArCH), 4.85 (1H, d, CHCl of β -lactam ring), 3.40 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 6b $\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 3 400 (NH), 1 650 (C=O), 1 760 (C=O of β -lactam ring), δ (CDCl₃) 8.75-7.30 (1H, bs, CONH exchangeable), 10.50 (1H, ss, ArOH exchangeable), 6.55 (1H, s, ArCH), 5.70 (1H, q, CH₂CH), 4.90 (3H, d, CH₂CH of thialactam), 3.37 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7a $\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 3 400 (NH), 1 500 (C-N), 1 429 (N=N), 1 590 cm⁻¹ (C=N), δ (CDCl₃) 8.90-7.50 (13H, m, ArH), 10.50 (1H, ss, ArOH exchangeable), 6.95 (1H, bs, NHC=O exchangeable), 7b $\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 3 400 (NH), 1 590 (C=N), 1 429 cm⁻¹ (N=N), δ (CDCl₃) 8.90-7.50 (13H, m, ArH), 10.50 (1H, ss, ArOH exchangeable), 6.95 (1H, bs, CONH exchangeable), 3.37 (3H, s, OCH₃).

spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a JMS D-300 instrument with -2000 DATA. Physical, analytical and spectral data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

General method of preparation of compounds 3a-h : An ethanolic mixture (50 ml) of 2 (0.01 mol) and substituted benzaldehydes (0.01 mol) containing a few drops of piperidine was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, and the resulting solid was washed with ether and recrystallised from appropriate solvents.

Cyclisation of compounds 3a-h to 4a-h : A solution of the hydrazones (3a-h ; 1 g) in dry THF

was treated with excess of dry and cooled ethereal diazomethane. The reaction mixture was maintained below 15° during which fresh amount of ethereal diazomethane was added. The ether was then evaporated and the resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and recrystallised from appropriate solvents.

Cyclocondensation of compounds 3a-h to 4a-h : To a cooled mixtures of 3a-h (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dry DMF (50 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) was added dropwise during 60 min with stirring and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature overnight followed by

refluxing for 6 h. The resulting solid was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated and poured into ice-cold water. The solid thus separated was recrystallised from appropriate solvents.

Cyclocondensation of compounds 3a-h to 6a-h : To a solution of the hydrazones (3a-h; 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) was added thiolactic acid (0.02 mol) dropwise with stirring at ambient temperature and the mixture was kept for 3 days at room temperature and refluxed for 6 h. It was then filtered and the filtrate concentrated and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was recrystallised from appropriate solvents.

Preparation of formazans (7a-h) : To the substituted anilines (2 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was added concentrated HCl (3 ml) at 0-5°. A solution of NaNO₂ (1 g in 5 ml water) was then added dropwise. The diazonium salt solution thus prepared was added dropwise with stirring in a solution of the hydrazones (3a-h; 2.4 g) in pyridine (50 ml) below 0°. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 3 days and then poured into cold water (250 ml). The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from appropriate solvents.

Cardiovascular activity : Cardiovascular activity of the compounds was tested by the reported method⁶. Out of 40 compounds, 3c-h, 4a-h, 5a-h, 6e-h and 7a, c, d, f, g, h exhibited hypotensive activity of varying degree (10-120 mm/Hg) and duration (10-120 min). The compound 3d showed consistent fall in blood pressure which lasted for 120 min in addition with abolition of CO along with the potentiation of NE response, and hence it

showed promising hypotensive activity. On the contrary, compound 7h induced hypertensive (120 mm/Hg) response which may be due to marked hypertension. Furthermore, none of the compounds except 3d and 7h could modify the pressor responses.

References

1. A. KUMAR, S. GURTU, J. N. SINHA, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. SHANKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 608; G. SATHI, V. R. GUJRATI, C. NATH, J. C. AGARWAL, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. SHANKER, *Arznein. Forsch.*, 1983, **33**, 9, 1218; M. A. A. ABBADY and M. A. EL-MAGHRABY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **54**, 44; M. A. ABBADY and M. A. EL-MAGHRABY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, **18**, 47, 413; M. A. ABBADY, A. M. OSMAN and F. M. ATTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981 **20**, 524.
2. M. SHARMA, K. SHANKER, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHORE, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1978, **67**, 165; A. R. SURREY and H. F. HAMMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 113; M. WRIZMAN and BOGRACHOV, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1222; J. C. GUPTA, B. S. KOHLI and A. JUTTA, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1944, **32**, 183; G. SATHI, V. S. GUJRATI, M. SHARMA, C. NATH, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. SHANKER, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1983, **316**, 767; B. S. JANDHYALA, C. G. J. GREY and J. P. BUCKLEY, *Arch. Int. Pharmacodyn.*, 1967, **168**, 127; S. K. MEO, B. PERRATA and M. H. SCHEVERS, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1949, **95**, 207.
3. A. KUMAR, B. P. JAJU, S. GURTU, J. N. SINHA and K. SHANKER, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 93.
4. H. R. SYNDER, H. F. FREIER, P. KOVACIK and F. M. V. HEYRINYEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 371.
5. A. KUMAR, J. C. AGARWAL, C. NATH, S. GURTU, J. N. SINHA, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. SHANKER, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1981, **18**, 1269.